

Ion Suppression Chromatographic Analysis of Saturated Lower Fatty Acids Present during Propionic Acid Fermentation

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Analysis of saturated lower fatty acids was made using a μ -bondapak C-18 column. Isocratic mobile phase used was 50 mM potassium phosphate buffer (pH 3.7) containing 5% (v/v) each of methanol and acetonitrile at a flow rate of 1 ml min^{-1} . The method needed no pre-derivatisation of acids and had sensitivity of detection as low as 1 μ mol of acid/ml. Lactate, usually present in propionic acid fermentation media, did not interfere in the estimation of acetic, propionic or butyric acids.

With the increasing fermentative production of propionic acid, simple and quick methods for its estimation are necessitated. The gas chromatography for this purpose has its own merits and demerits. Methods for the analysis of the acid by high-performance liquid chromatography (hplc) with¹ or without² pre-derivatisation of the acid have used ion-exchange columns for this purpose. Unfortunately, it never became possible for us to use ion-exchange column (Partisil 10SAX, 0.46 \times 25.0 cm; Whatman) with several mobile phases. This paper reports simple and quick hplc-method for the estimation of lower fatty acids (formic, acetic, propionic, butyric and lactic) which are present during propionic acid fermentation.

Results and Discussion

Mobile phase containing acetonitrile only gave a clear cut separation of all acids but peak tailing (peak asymmetry, A_s 1.8) was noticed mainly for butyric acid. Considering the fact that increase in solvent strength (E° against Al_2O_3 according to Snyder³) of the mobile phase might help in decreasing the peak tailing, mobile phase was modified by the inclusion of methanol. Thus modified mobile phase worked well for authentic samples but proved unsuitable for analysing crude fermented liquor. So fermented liquor as well as standard fatty acids were steam distilled which is also used for the recovery of lower fatty acids prior to gas chromatography.

The recovery of propionic acid and butyric acid by steam distillation exceeded 80–90% (w/w), while those for formic and acetic acids ranged between 40 and 50% (w/w). Both propionic acid (RT=7.85 min) and butyric acid (RT=15.03 min) could be efficiently separated from the mixtures. Steam distillate of best produced fermented liquor contained primarily propionic acid which was confirmed by cochromatography with authentic acid sample.

All chromatographic separation of low carbon

fatty acids were done in presence or in absence of lactic acid or sodium lactate (Table 1). Presence or absence of lactate during chromatographic separation was checked since lactate is normally used in the media for the fermentative production of propionic acid. It is evident from Table 1 that all of these acids are effectively separated within 14.6 min. Both propionic and butyric acids are major components of the fermented liquor and so standard curves for these fatty acids were drawn which are linear (Fig. 1). Authenticity of this method was verified by paper chromatography. Samples containing as low as 1.0 μ mol ml^{-1} of either acids could be determined by this technique.

TABLE 1—HPLC SEPARATION OF SATURATED VOLATILE FATTY ACIDS IN PRESENCE OR IN ABSENCE OF LACTATE

Mixture containing	Retention time (min)				
	Formic acid	Lactate	Acetic acid	Propionic acid	Butyric acid
No lactate	4.36	—	5.22	7.62	14.60
Lactic acid	4.77	5.83 ^a	5.25	7.65	14.60
Sod. lactate	4.60	3.96 ^a	5.08	7.45	14.41

^aDifference was observed due to presence of salt or free acid of lactate. 20–200 μ l of samples containing 0.5 μ mol each of all acids were injected. Values represent average of 3 injections. Retention times never varied more than 0.5% between injections of similar samples. However, retention time increased by 3% when sample volume was increased by 10-fold.

Analysis of steam distillates obtained from various fermented liquors was also performed. Amount of propionic acid detected from the fermented liquors of media numbers 1–5 were 5.5, 1.42, 1.82, 3.08, 0.42 mmol ml^{-1} respectively. The fermented liquors obtained using media 4 and 5 contained very little propionic acid but contained formic acid and some unidentified peaks. None of these samples contained any butyric acid.

Fig. 1. Standard curve of acids: (O) propionic acid and (Δ) butyric acid; solution ($10 \mu\text{mol ml}^{-1}$ each) were co-chromatographed by injecting 60–500 μl samples.

Experimental

All solvents (Spectrochem., India) were commercial hplc grade materials and fatty acids were of highly purified grades. Hplc (Waters) system consisting of 501 pumps fitted with a 680 programmer, 484 LC spectrophotometer and 745B data module was used. Hplc column used was a Radial-PAK cartridge with μ -bondapak C18 packing, 0.8×10 cm, taken in a Z-module (Waters). Absorbance was monitored at 210 nm. Isocratic separation was achieved at ambient temperature ($25-30^\circ$) using 50 mM potassium phosphate buffer containing 7.0% acetonitrile (v/v), pH 3.5 or 50 mM potassium phosphate containing 5.0% acetonitrile, 5.0% methanol (v/v), pH 3.5. Flow rate used was 1 ml min^{-1} . Peak areas ($\text{area} \times 10^{-6}$) were obtained from the 745B data module print-out which

was adjusted to: attenuation=256; chart speed = 0.25 cm min^{-1} . Values represented were the average of two sets of injections.

Samples were prepared by steam distillation. Either known fatty acids or unknown mixtures (0.5 ml) were brought to pH 1.5–1.8 by H_2SO_4 before distillation. Distilled acids were collected in a final volume of 10.0–13.0 ml.

A strain of *Propionibacterium*, isolated in the laboratory, was grown under stationary condition in an incubation room at $30 \pm 1^\circ$ in five different media⁴ of compositions (% w/v): (i) yeast extract, 1.0; sodium lactate, 4.0; pH 6.5, (ii) yeast extract, 0.33; KH_2PO_4 , 0.27, K_2HPO_4 , 0.4, $\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 1.0×10^{-3} , calcium pantothenate, 1.0×10^{-4} ; thiamine-HCl, 1.0×10^{-4} ; D-biotin, 6.67×10^{-5} ; glucose, 0.5, (iii) potato extract, 20; K_2HPO_4 , 0.5, trypticase soya broth, 0.5; yeast extract, 0.7; glucose, 2.0; pH 7.5, (iv) yeast extract, 1.0; KH_2PO_4 , 1.0; $\text{Na}_2\text{HPO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 3.0; sodium lactate, 0.28; pH 7.0, (v) yeast extract, 1.0; KH_2PO_4 , 0.1; $\text{Na}_2\text{HPO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 0.3; sodium lactate, 0.28; pH 7.0. Growths were continued till 2–3 days after inoculation ($A_{600} = 0.5$) and culture filtrates were subjected to fatty acid analysis.

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